

Triterpenoids : XL. The Structure of Lantic Acid - A New Triterpene from *Lantana camara*

A. K. BARUA, (MISS) P. CHAKRABARTI, P. K. SANYAL, K. BASU & K. NAG

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Calcutta-9

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The structure of Lantic acid—a new triterpene from the leaves of *Lantana camara* was earlier proposed as (I). Lantic acid has now been converted to 3-keto methyl ursolate and this finally establish the structure of lantic acid as (I) as proposed earlier.

In our previous communications the isolation of new triterpene acids called lantanolic acid^{1,2} and lantic acid³ from the leaves of *Lantana camara* was reported. The structure (I) was proposed for lantic acid. Lantic acid was converted to 3-deoxy methyl ursolate which clearly established the nature of the carbon skeleton and the location of the carboxyl group in lantic acid. The potential keto group in lantic acid was considered to be at C-3 because the keto-aldehyde (IIb) obtained by oxidation of the diol (IIa)³ gave positive Zimmermann colour test for a 3-keto group⁴. But the possibility of the keto group being at C-2 could not, however, be completely overruled on the basis of the above colour reaction only. Thus another alternative structure (III) had to be considered for lantic acid. To decide finally between the two structures (I) and (III) some further experiments have been carried out and are presented here.

The keto-aldehyde (IIb) furnished a mono-ketal (IVa), $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_5$ (M^+ 526), m.p. 235°–36°, on treatment with ethylene glycol and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid in benzene. The n.m.r. spectrum of the mono-ketal (IVa) showed a signal at 10.2 δ (S, 1H) for the free aldehydic

proton and the signal for the four protons of the ethylenedioxy group (O-CH₂-CH₂-O-) appeared at 3.93 δ (S, 4H). Wolff-Kishner reduction of the ketal (IVa) under anhydrous conditions⁵ followed by esterification with diazomethane furnished a compound, C₃₃H₅₂O₄, m.p. 250°-52°. This was characterized as the ketal (IVb) of 3-keto methyl ursolate which on treatment with ethanolic hydrochloric acid furnished 3-keto-methyl ursolate (IIc).

The conversion of lantic acid to 3-keto methyl ursolate clearly established that the potential keto group in lantic acid is at C-3. Hence the structure of lantic acid should be represented as (I) proposed earlier.

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